

Stability Optimization of Laminated Composite Plates under In-Plane Loads

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ABSTRACT

This paper is concerned with the stability optimization of orthotropic laminated composite plates under compression, shear or combined loads. The plates considered are rectangular and the boundary conditions are simply supported or clamped.

The buckling characteristics of the orthotropic laminated plates are examined by introducing stiffness invariants and two lamination parameters. The optimal laminate configuration which gives the highest buckling load is found by utilizing mathematical optimization techniques for the various aspect ratios of the plates under combined loads.

1. INTRODUCTION

The buckling characteristics of composite plates depend highly on fiber directions. Therefore, it is important to tailor the laminate configuration of the composite plates.

Housner and Stein (1) made a parametric study to find the best fiber directions which gave the highest buckling load for angle-ply laminated plates under combined compression and shear. One of the authors (2,3) found the optimal fiber directions of simply-supported laminated plates under compression or shear by using an optimization technique. One of his conclusions is that an angle-ply laminate gives the highest buckling load, even if almost complete freedom is given in the selection of fiber directions. However, it is yet unknown whether angle-ply laminates are the best or not under combined loads or other boundary conditions.

In the present paper, the optimization problems of the laminated plates under buckling constraints are treated more generally. Coupling stiffnesses such as bending-extension etc. are neglected in this analysis, because it is shown numerically (4,5) or analytically (6) that the buckling loads of the laminates with these coupling stiffnesses are lower than those of the laminates without them. Neglecting coupling stiffnesses, we obtain the equation of the classical orthotropic plates. The equation is rewritten by introducing stiffness invariants (7) and two lamination parameters on out-of-plane stiffnesses (6,8). These lamination parameters on out-of-plane stiffnesses are the extension of those on in-plane stiffnesses suggested by Miki (8).

It is shown that the buckling of the laminated plates is characterized by

two lamination parameters. Mathematical optimization techniques are utilized to find the laminate configuration which gives the highest buckling load.

2. BUCKLING CHARACTERISTICS OF LAMINATED COMPOSITE PLATES

2.1 Buckling Equation of Laminated Composite Plates

The laminate considered is composed of many layers and each layer is assumed to have the same thickness and an equal number of fibers in the $+0_i$ and -0_i directions with respect to the plate axis. Therefore, the coupling stiffnesses A_{16} , A_{26} , B_{16} , B_{26} , D_{16} , D_{26} can be neglected. The remaining coupling stiffnesses are B_{11} , B_{12} , B_{22} , B_{66} and these coupling stiffnesses reduce the buckling load for the case of the simply-supported (S2 boundary conditions) plates under axial compression as shown in appendix. For other cases than S2 boundary conditions, it is shown in (6) that the coupling stiffnesses reduce the buckling load. Therefore, we can neglect bending-extension coupling. This means that the plates considered are midplane symmetric laminates.

The buckling equation of the plates shown in Fig.1 is given as follows.

$$D_{11}w_{,xxxx} + 2(D_{12} + 2D_{66})w_{,xxyy} + D_{22}w_{,yyyy} = -\bar{N}_x w_{,xx} - \bar{N}_y w_{,yy} + 2\bar{N}_{xy} w_{,xy} \quad (1)$$

where a comma denotes the differentiation of the principal symbol with respect to the subscript. \bar{N}_x , \bar{N}_y and \bar{N}_{xy} are stress resultants.

The following two boundary conditions are considered in this analysis.

(a) Simply-supported edge boundary conditions

$$x = 0, a ; w = w_{,xx} = 0 \quad , \quad y = 0, b ; w = w_{,yy} = 0 \quad (2)$$

(b) Clamped edge boundary conditions

$$x = 0, a ; w = w_{,x} = 0 \quad , \quad y = 0, b ; w = w_{,y} = 0 \quad (3)$$

Substitution of stiffness invariants U_i ($i=1,2,\dots,5$) (7) and introduction of lamination parameters on out-of-plane stiffnesses (6,8) in Eq.(1) give

$$P_1(w) + P_2(w) \alpha + P_3(w) \beta = -\bar{N}_x w_{,xx} - \bar{N}_y w_{,yy} + 2\bar{N}_{xy} w_{,xy} \quad (4)$$

where

$$\left. \begin{aligned} P_1(w) &= [(U_1 - U_3)(w_{,xxxx} + w_{,yyyy}) + 2(3U_3 + U_4 + 2U_5)w_{,xxyy}] h^3/12 \\ P_2(w) &= U_2[w_{,xxxx} - w_{,yyyy}] h^3/12 \\ P_3(w) &= U_3[w_{,xxxx} - 6w_{,xxyy} + w_{,yyyy}] h^3/6 \\ \alpha &\equiv \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} \cos 2\theta(z) z^2 dz / (h^3/12) \quad , \quad \beta \equiv \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} \cos^2 2\theta(z) z^2 dz / (h^3/12) \\ U_1 &= (3Q_{11} + 3Q_{22} + 2Q_{12} + 4Q_{66})/8 \quad , \quad U_2 = (Q_{11} - Q_{22})/2 \\ U_3 &= (Q_{11} + Q_{22} - 2Q_{12} - 4Q_{66})/8 \quad , \quad U_4 = (Q_{11} + Q_{22} + 6Q_{12} - 4Q_{66})/8 \\ U_5 &= (Q_{11} + Q_{22} - 2Q_{12} + 4Q_{66})/8 \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (5)$$

where h denotes the thickness of the plate. It should be noted that θ is a function of z . The lamination parameters α and β express the effects of the stacking sequence.

2.2 Characteristics of Lamination Parameters

Assuming midplane symmetric laminates and introducing u which is given by

Fig.1. Configuration of the laminated plate.

$u=z/(h/2)$, we get

$$\alpha = 3 \int_0^1 \cos 2\theta(u) u^2 du, \quad \beta = 3 \int_0^1 \cos^2 2\theta(u) u^2 du \quad (6)$$

The following equations are obtained from Eqs.(6), since $\int_0^1 [\cos 2\theta(u) - \alpha]^2 u^2 du \geq 0$.

$$-1 \leq \alpha \leq 1, \quad \alpha^2 \leq \beta \leq 1 \quad (7)$$

These relations are shown in a shaded region in Fig.2(a). General cross-ply laminates, which consist of 0° layers and 90° layers, are expressed by $\beta=1$, and angle-ply laminates, which consist of $+\theta_1$ layers and $-\theta_1$ layers, are expressed by $\beta=\alpha^2$. The relation between α and θ in angle-ply laminates is shown in Fig.2(b). The relation between α and the thickness of 90° layers h_{90} in cross-ply laminates which have 0° outer layers and 90° inner layers is shown in Fig.2(c).

It is expected from Fig.2(a) that either an angle-ply or a cross-ply laminate gives the highest buckling load, because the buckling equation (4) is a linear function of α and β .

We consider the laminate $[0/\pm\theta_0]_{\text{sym}}$, which have 0° outer layers (the thickness h_0) and $\pm\theta_0$ inner layers (the thickness $h_{\theta_0}=1-h_0$), and express θ_0 and h_{θ_0} by α and β . The intersection of $\beta=\alpha^2$ and a straight line which connects (α,β) and $(1,1)$ are denoted by (α_0,β_0) as shown in Fig.3. The values of α_0 and β_0 are obtained as follows.

$$\alpha_0 = (\alpha - \beta) / (1 - \alpha), \quad \beta_0 = \alpha_0^2 \quad (8)$$

Eqs.(8) give the fiber direction θ_0 which corresponds to (α_0,β_0) .

$$\theta_0 = \frac{1}{2} \cos^{-1}((\alpha - \beta) / (1 - \alpha)) \quad (9)$$

By using Eq.(6), the following equations are obtained.

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \alpha \\ \beta \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} \alpha_0 \\ \beta_0 \end{Bmatrix} \bar{h}_{\theta_0} + \begin{Bmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \end{Bmatrix} h_0 \quad (10)$$

where $\bar{h}_{\theta_0} = h_{\theta_0}^3$ and $\bar{h}_0 = 1 - \bar{h}_{\theta_0}$.

The values α and β which are given by Eqs.(10) correspond to the coordinates of the point which divides the straight line between (α_0,β_0) and $(1,1)$ in a ratio of $\bar{h}_0:\bar{h}_{\theta_0}$. From Eqs.(10), we get

$$h_{\theta_0} = \sqrt[3]{(1-\alpha)^2 / (1-2\alpha+\beta)}, \quad h_0 = 1 - h_{\theta_0} \quad (11)$$

The above equations (9) and (11) show that a laminate configuration $[0/\pm\theta_0]_{\text{sym}}$ can express an arbitrary laminate configuration expressed by α and β . Therefore, it can be said that the characteristics of any laminate expressed by two lamination parameters α and β are also obtained by the $[0/\pm\theta_0]_{\text{sym}}$ laminate.

2.3 Buckling Characteristics of Simply-Supported Plates under Axial Compression

By neglecting the coupling stiffnesses B_{11} , B_{12} , B_{22} , B_{66} in Eq.(A6) in appendix, the following normalized compressive buckling load is obtained.

(a) The region occupied by (α,β) .

(b) The relation between α and θ in angle-ply laminates.

(c) The relation between α and h_{90} in cross-ply laminates.

Fig.2. Characteristics of lamination parameters (α,β) .

Fig.3. The relation between (α,β) and $[0/\pm\theta_0]_{\text{sym}}$ laminate.

$$\Phi \equiv \frac{12b^2\bar{N}_x}{\pi^2 Q_{22} h^3} = \frac{(b/a)^2}{Q_{22}[m^2 + k_y n^2 (a/b)^2]} [C_1 + C_2 \alpha + C_3 \beta] \quad (12)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} C_1 &= (U_1 - U_3)m^4 + (U_1 - U_3)n^4 (a/b)^4 + 2(3U_3 + U_4 + 2U_5)m^2 n^2 (a/b)^2 \\ C_2 &= U_2[m^4 - n^4 (a/b)^4], \quad C_3 = 2U_3[m^4 + n^4 (a/b)^4 - 6m^2 n^2 (a/b)^2] \\ k_y &= \bar{N}_y / \bar{N}_x \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

where m and n are the number of buckling half waves in the x - and y -directions, respectively. The smallest value of Φ for m and n is the critical buckling load. In Eq.(12), C_3 is generally negative because a/m is nearly equal to b/n , unless a/b is extremely different from 1.

For the given value of α , we have the highest buckling load when β has the minimum value. The minimum value corresponds to the case that β is equal to α^2 . Therefore, it can be said that the best laminate configuration which gives the highest buckling load of the simply-supported plates exists among angle-ply laminates.

3. BUCKLING ANALYSES IN GENERAL CASES AND METHODS OF OPTIMIZATION

3.1 Buckling Analyses of the Plates

For the simply-supported plates under compression, the closed-form formula for the buckling load could be obtained in the previous section. But generally, the closed-form solution can not be obtained for the plates under combined loads or of the clamped boundary conditions. Therefore, the following displacement functions which satisfy the simply-supported or clamped-supported boundary conditions are assumed.

(a) For simply-supported edges,

$$w(x,y) = \sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{n=1}^N W_{mn} \sin(m\pi x/a) \sin(n\pi y/b) \quad (14)$$

(b) For clamped edges,

$$w(x,y) = \sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{n=1}^N W_{mn} [\cos((m-1)\pi x/a) - \cos((m+1)\pi x/a)] \times [\cos((n-1)\pi y/b) - \cos((n+1)\pi y/b)] \quad (15)$$

Applying Galerkin method to Eq.(4), we obtain the homogeneous set of algebraic equations with respect to W_{mn} . The critical buckling load is given by the lowest eigenvalue of the coefficient matrix of these equations.

3.2 Optimization Techniques for Seeking the Highest Buckling Load

In the case of the simply-supported plates under compression, an angle-ply laminate gives the highest buckling load as discussed in the previous section. Then the optimal laminate configuration can be found by a mathematical optimization method. The method used for this case is the golden section search method (9) and the design variable is the fiber direction θ .

In other cases, angle-ply laminates are not necessarily the best ones. Therefore, it is unknown where the optimal laminate configuration is located on α - β plane. It is already known that $[0/\pm\theta_0]_{\text{sym}}$ laminate can express the characteristics of all kinds of the laminates. We can use h_0 and θ_0 to express the buckling characteristics instead of α and β . Further we introduce x_1 and x_2 given by the following equations.

$$h_0 = \sin^2 x_1, \quad \theta_0 = \pi/2 \sin^2 x_2 \quad (16)$$

Using x_1 and x_2 as design variables, we can find the highest buckling load by applying a multivariable optimization technique. The technique selected is the simplex method (9).

4. NUMERICAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The following elastic constants for carbon/epoxy composites are used for numerical examples.

(a) $k_y = 0$

(b) $k_y = 0.5$

Fig.4. Variations of the normalized compressive buckling load with lamination parameter α .

(a) Simply-supported.

(b) Clamped.

Fig.5. The contours of the normalized compressive buckling load for $a/b=2.0$ and $k_y=0.5$ on α - β plane.

Fig.6. The optimal fiber directions and the normalized buckling loads for the case of the simply-supported plates under compression.

$$E_L = 142 \text{ GPa} , E_T = 10.8 \text{ GPa} , G_{LT} = 5.49 \text{ GPa} , \nu_L = 0.30 \quad (17)$$

The buckling loads were calculated by taking $M=N=7$ in Eqs.(14) and (15).

4.1 Compressive Buckling Characteristics and the Optimal Laminate Configuration

The normalized buckling loads for two kinds of compressive load ratios $k_y = \bar{N}_y / \bar{N}_x$ are shown in Figs.4(a) and 4(b). These figures show that the angle-ply laminate gives higher buckling load than the cross-ply laminate for the case of the simply-supported edges. But for the case of the clamped edges, simple conclusions cannot be drawn.

The contours of the normalized compressive buckling loads ϕ for $a/b=2.0$ and $k_y=0.5$ are shown on α - β plane in Fig.5. For the case of the simply-supported edges, the contours consist of piece-wise linear lines and the buckling mode parameters (m,n) are shown in parentheses in Fig.5(a). For the case of the clamped edges, the contours consist of curved lines as shown in Fig.5(b).

Fig.6 shows the optimal fiber directions and the normalized buckling loads for the case of the simply-supported plates under compression. The optimal fiber directions for $a/b=1.0$ are $\pm 45^\circ$ even if the load ratios k_y vary from 0 to 4. The optimal fiber directions for $a/b=2.0$ highly depend on the load ratios.

The highest buckling loads under biaxial compression are shown in Fig.7. Open circles denote angle-ply laminates and the optimal fiber directions are also shown beside the open circles. Solid circles denote cross-ply laminates and the optimal lamination parameters α are also shown beside the solid circles.

It is interesting to note that a cross-ply laminate gives the optimal laminate configuration for the case of the clamped plates with $a/b=1.0$.

4.2 Shear Buckling Characteristics and the Optimal Laminate Configuration

The highest buckling loads under shear are shown in Fig.8. An angle-ply laminate gives the optimal laminate configuration for the case of both the simply-supported and the clamped edges. The optimal fiber directions vary from 45° to 60° with the aspect ratios.

Fig.9 shows the highest buckling loads and the corresponding optimal fiber directions for the laminated plates under axial compression and shear. Also in this case, an angle-ply laminate gives the optimal laminate configuration. For the case of the clamped plates with $a/b=1.0$, the optimal fiber directions vary from 0° at $\bar{N}_{xy}=0$ to 45° at $\bar{N}_x=0$.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The optimal laminate configurations are found for the orthotropic laminated composite plates under compression, shear or combined loads, by utilizing mathematical optimization techniques. The conclusions obtained are as follows.

- (1) An angle-ply laminate gives the optimal laminate configuration for the case of the simply-supported plates under compression, shear or combined loads.
- (2) Either an angle-ply or a cross-ply laminate gives the optimal laminate configuration for the case of the clamped plates.

Fig.7. The normalized buckling loads and the optimal laminate configurations under biaxial compression.

Fig. 8. The optimum fiber directions and the normalized shear buckling load under shear.

Fig. 9. The normalized buckling load and the optimum fiber directions under combined axial compression and shear.

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APPENDIX Coupling Effects of Simply-Supported Plates under Compression

The bending-extension coupling effects on the compressive buckling loads for the case of S2 boundary conditions are examined. The buckling equations and the boundary conditions can be written as follows.

$$\left. \begin{aligned} A_{11}u_{,xx} + A_{66}u_{,yy} + (A_{12}+A_{66})v_{,xy} - B_{11}w_{,xxx} - (B_{12}+2B_{66})w_{,xyy} &= 0 \\ (A_{12}+A_{66})u_{,xy} + A_{66}v_{,xx} + A_{22}v_{,yy} - (B_{12}+2B_{66})w_{,xxy} - B_{22}w_{,yyy} &= 0 \\ D_{11}w_{,xxxx} + 2(D_{12}+2D_{66})w_{,xxyy} + D_{22}w_{,yyyy} - B_{11}u_{,xxx} \\ - (B_{12}+2B_{66})u_{,xyy} - (B_{12}+2B_{66})v_{,xxy} - B_{22}v_{,yyy} = -\bar{N}_x w_{,xx} - \bar{N}_y w_{,yy} \end{aligned} \right\} \text{(A1)}$$

$$x = 0, a; \quad N_x = v = w = M_x = 0, \quad y = 0, b; \quad N_y = u = w = M_y = 0 \quad \text{(A2)}$$

The following displacement functions satisfy the boundary conditions given by Eq.(A2).

$$\left. \begin{aligned} u &= -U_{mn} \cos(m\pi x/a) \sin(n\pi y/b), \quad v = -V_{mn} \sin(m\pi x/a) \cos(n\pi y/b) \\ w &= W_{mn} \sin(m\pi x/a) \sin(n\pi y/b) \end{aligned} \right\} \text{(A3)}$$

Substitution of Eq.(A3) into Eqs.(A1) gives

$$\begin{pmatrix} T_{11} & T_{12} & T_{13} \\ T_{12} & T_{22} & T_{23} \\ T_{13} & T_{23} & T_{33} \end{pmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} U_{mn} \\ V_{mn} \\ W_{mn} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ (\lambda^2 + k_y \mu^2) \bar{N}_x W_{mn} \end{Bmatrix} \quad \text{(A4)}$$

where,

$$\left. \begin{aligned} T_{11} &= A_{11}\lambda^2 + A_{66}\mu^2, \quad T_{12} = (A_{12} + A_{66})\lambda\mu, \quad T_{13} = B_{11}\lambda^3 + (B_{12} + 2B_{66})\lambda\mu^2 \\ T_{22} &= A_{66}\lambda^2 + A_{22}\mu^2, \quad T_{23} = (B_{12} + 2B_{66})\lambda^2\mu + B_{22}\mu^3 \\ T_{33} &= D_{11}\lambda^4 + 2(D_{12} + 2D_{66})\lambda^2\mu^2 + D_{22}\mu^4, \quad \lambda = m\pi/a, \quad \mu = n\pi/b, \quad k_y = \bar{N}_y/\bar{N}_x \end{aligned} \right\} \text{(A5)}$$

Equating the determinant of Eqs.(A4) to zero gives

$$\bar{N}_x = \frac{1}{\lambda^2 + k_y \mu^2} \left[T_{33} - \begin{Bmatrix} T_{13} \\ T_{23} \end{Bmatrix}^T \begin{Bmatrix} T_{11} & T_{12} \\ T_{12} & T_{22} \end{Bmatrix}^{-1} \begin{Bmatrix} T_{13} \\ T_{23} \end{Bmatrix} \right] \quad \text{(A6)}$$

The smallest value of \bar{N}_x for various m and n is the buckling load. The matrix $\begin{Bmatrix} T_{11} & T_{12} \\ T_{12} & T_{22} \end{Bmatrix}^{-1}$ in Eq.(A6) is positive definite, since $T_{11} > 0$ and $T_{11}T_{22} - T_{12}^2 > 0$.

Therefore, the second term on the right-hand side of Eq.(A6) shows the reduction of the buckling load due to bending-extension coupling.